

ENERGY ABSORBING COMPOSITE JOINTS AND THEIR APPLICATION TO NOISE REDUCED SONAR DOMES.

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SUMMARY: This paper concerns the noise and vibration advantages of an energy absorbing composite joint and its relevance to noise reduced glass reinforced polyester (GRP) sonar domes. Once installed on an operational boat, hydrodynamic flow and supporting structural induced vibrations cause the dome to vibrate thus radiating noise and interfering with sonar sensor response. The results of a vibration transmissibility study on a glass reinforced polyester/steel interface are discussed as the first step in designing a composite viscoelastic joint that can act as a vibration sink to absorb flow generated and structureborne noise within GRP sonar domes. Preliminary investigations concerning the absorption of compressional waves by use of a tapered viscoelastic interlayer are discussed. It is shown that a tapered viscoelastic interlayer placed between a GRP beam and steel supporting substrate can produce a significant absorption of vibrational energy, reducing waterborne radiated noise and providing a significantly quieter noise platform than conventional sonar jointing technology.

KEYWORDS: composite joints, energy absorption, noise reduction, damage tolerance, fatigue resistance.

INTRODUCTION

Sonar systems are now used for a variety of applications whether it be for the detection of enemy ships in naval applications, sub bottom profiling in oceanographic surveys or for fish location and identification. Those sonar systems are invariably enclosed within a dome fabricated in Glass Reinforced Polyester (GRP) composite.

For effective operation it is essential that the sonar platform be as free from noise and vibration as possible. However, one potential source of sonar platform noise is the dome itself. Flow induced noise and that generated within the supporting structure can cause the dome itself to generate waterborne sound and interfere with the sonar sensors. It is suggested that one way of reducing this interference may be by the incorporation of a viscoelastic interlayer between the dome and supporting structure to act as an acoustic sink to all structureborne vibrations in this area.

The purpose of this paper is to present some preliminary laboratory findings obtained from the use of tapered viscoelastic interlayers between GRP/steel interfaces. It is known that for typical sonar dome thicknesses and sonar operational frequencies it is the compressional waves and not the flexural waves that are the dominant source of noise. Thus as a first stage this investigation the concerns compressional waves only.

BACKGROUND

Essentially the problem of acoustic interaction at the joint between a GRP sonar dome and its (often) steel supporting structure can be outlined as follows. Turbulent-flow induced energy can couple into the GRP dome. That vibrational energy will propagate along the GRP until the steel joint interface is reached where one or a combination of effects occur:

- (a) vibrational energy is reflected back along the GRP, mode conversion possibly taking place, the compressional waves in particular being free to radiate as waterborne sound into the sonar sensor space.
- (b) energy is transmitted through the joint into the steel supporting structure. However, more importantly energy in the form of compressional and/or flexural waves from the steel support side can propagate into the GRP where once again the compressional waves are free to radiate into the sensor site and acoustic energy will be emitted at the impedance discontinuity caused by the dissimilar materials of the GRP/steel interface.

The acoustic interaction at a simple joint between dissimilar materials has been studied in [1-3] so it is not intended to discuss this in detail here. Briefly, the references show that high vibrational reflection losses* can be obtained at a GRP/steel interface provided the joint input impedance is matched. This is generally coupled with a low transmission loss*. Conversely, it is possible to obtain a high transmission loss but at the expense of a good reflection loss. In all these cases vibrational energy is not lost or absorbed but merely redirected or altered by mode conversion. An alternative approach is to provide a joint that actually absorbs the energy. It is suggested that this may best be achieved by use of a viscoelastic polymeric interlayer between the GRP and steel to act as an acoustic sink .

THE VISCOELASTIC JOINT

It can be shown theoretically [2] that the reflection and transmission loss for compressional waves at or across a two layer interface is dependant on the input impedance of the second layer, this is given by the following transmission line equation:

$$Z_{in} = Z [(Z_1 \cosh(\alpha+jk)x + Z \sinh(\alpha+jk)x) / (Z \cosh(\alpha+jk)x + Z_1 \sinh(\alpha+jk)x)] \quad (1)$$

where Z_{in} = the input impedance at the joint interface

Z_1 = the characteristic impedance of the termination

Z = the complex characteristic impedance of the layer (joint)

x = the thickness of the layer α = the attenuation constant of the layer

k = the wave number ($2\pi f/c$) c = the complex wave velocity

f = the frequency

This has been incorporated into a computer program which will model single and multilayer laminar structure.

Use of the multilayer programme demonstrated that a simple solid viscoelastic polymeric interlayer does not have the ideal characteristic impedance for a vibration sink. This is because the polymer is not being allowed to deform or worked upon in such a way as to make

maximun use of its viscoelastic nature. The polymer needed to be more compliant and this was best achieved by the inclusion of air into the polymer thus making it in the form of a closed cell foam. A subprogram was used to allow the incorporation of compliant inclusions such air bubbles to modify the wave velocity and density and hence its characteristic impedance. Kerners theory ^[4] has been used to calculate the effective wave velocity of the polymer assuming prior knowledge of the bulk modulus, dynamic shear modulus, poissons ratio and volume fraction of air.

Thus:

$$c_{eff} = \sqrt{[(K_{eff} + 4\mu_{eff}/3)/((1-\phi)\rho)]} \tag{2}$$

$$\text{where } K_{eff} = [(K(1-\phi)/(1+3k\phi/4\mu)] \tag{3}$$

$$\mu_{eff} = [\mu/1+(\phi/15(1-\sigma)/((1-\phi)(7-\sigma)))] \tag{4}$$

where: K = polymer bulk modulus K_{eff} = effective bulk modulus of the layer

μ_{eff} = effective shear modulus of the layer ϕ = volume fraction of air

σ = Poisson's ratio of polymer ρ = polymer density

μ = polymer shear modulus

The values of μ and K are of course complex but for simplicities sake K has been taken as real for all frequencies. The Poisson's ratio is assumed to be 0.4996 (i.e. a typical value for unfilled rubbers).

A prediction using this model is shown in figure 1, illustrating reflection and transmission loss as a function of frequency for a simple polymeric laminar interlayer.

Fig. 1: Reflection and transmission loss at GRP/Steel Interface with interlayer.

The interlayer between the steel and GRP is a nitrile rubber layer (AML3186) 250mm thick. The predictions assume the rubber has a 0.02 volume fraction of air typical for most rubber mouldings. This material has been selected deliberately as it is known to be in the middle of its molecular mainchain transition region (i.e. highly viscoelastic) over the temperature range 0 to 15C at frequencies between 1 to 20kHz (3 to 4.3 on log scale). Its dynamic physical properties of the polymer are shown in figures 2 and 3.

Clearly illustrated in figure 1 are the reflection loss peaks which occur at multiples of half wavelengths and are indicative of layer with a wave velocity of 1700m/s. These peaks are seen to be narrow band below 12kHz (4.08 on log scale) with low reflection loss minima of only 4dB at ~6kHz. Broadband reflection loss of 10dB is only achieved above 20kHz. This layer may only be useful in the high frequency range where the layer contains many multiples of half wavelengths. The transmission loss, never falls below 17dB above 1kHz (3 on log scale). It would be possible to improve the low frequency performance of this layer by making it thicker, thus inducing the halfwave resonances at lower frequencies. However, this may be impractical and the best compromise may be to make the layer three half wavelengths thick as per the prediction in figure 1

Fig. 2: Dynamic Youngs Modulus

Fig. 3: Loss Factor

where it has been set for 12kHz. One technique for overcoming the narrowband reflection loss at low frequencies is that of geometric impedance matching. This is a popular technique used in the design of anechoic linings for non-reverberant acoustic chambers. It involves the shaping of the layer in the form of a wedge such that the compressional waves in the GRP enter the viscoelastic layer gradually. Theoretical treatment of wedges is not trivial but a simple approximation may be made by assuming the 250mm layer to be divided into 16 layers as shown in figure 4.

Each layer is assumed to be 10mm thick consisting of part GRP and part viscoelastic polymer, the ratio of GRP to viscoelastic polymer gradually decreasing until it is entirely polymer. The all polymer layer (layer No 1) is 100mm thick. A linear law of mixtures can then be applied to calculate the characteristic impedance of each layer thus:

$$Z_L = Z_{GRP}\phi_{GRP} + Z\phi \tag{5}$$

where Z_L = characteristic impedance of the composite layer

Z_{GRP} = characteristic impedance of the GRP.

Z = characteristic impedance of the viscoelastic polymer.

ϕ_{GRP} = volume fraction of GRP in the layer.

ϕ = volume fraction of viscoelastic polymer in the layer.

Fig. 4: Composite viscoelastic wedge as modelled

Tapering the joint in this way not only improves the impedance matching of the layer but also provides a more structurally sound joint by allowing a larger surface area for bonding. Results for this form of joint are shown in figure 5.

Fig. 5: Transmission and reflection loss for viscoelastic wedge joint.

The reflection loss is now 10dB from 8kHz and above and the dips have now been eliminated. The transmission loss is still good with less evidence of the thicknesswise resonances. In fact tapering the joint layer in this way has resulted in a shift of the halfwave resonances to higher frequencies in this case from 3.4kHz to 4.4kHz. These results looked sufficiently encouraging to investigate a practical version of the joint.

A Practical Joint

For this exercise investigations were carried out on simple GRP beams 70mm wide by 25mm thick. The joint as constructed, consisted of a wedge of a high density (density - 1700kgm^{-3}), 80 IRHD nitrile rubber. The tapered part was 150mm long backed by a layer 100mm long and 50mm thick as shown in figure 6. To improve the joint structural integrity, a groove 6mm wide and 135mm deep was cut into the base of the wedge. The wedge was then bonded to a corresponding steel tongue which is in turn bolted to a steel beam.

Fig. 6: The composite viscoelastic wedge as tested.

Experimental Assessment

The experimental tests have divided into two parts:

- (a) Assessment of structureborne compressional waves.
- Waterborne noise radiation assessment.

Structureborne Assessment

This was intended to confirm, at least in trend, the predictions made above. The assessment was carried out at a temperature of 10C (bearing in mind the temperature sensitivity of the dynamic physical characteristics of the polymer) using the instrumentation illustrated in fig.7. A small transducer was attached end on to the GRP beam (in such a way as to excite compressional waves) with a lightweight accelerometer attached alongside. The transducer was excited with tone bursts where the tone frequency was varied between 5 to 12kHz. The accelerometer was used to monitor the burst after it had reflected from the far end of the beam with the joint attached. The reflection loss was established by comparing the returned signal with that from a similar sized GRP beam with no viscoelastic joint (assuming that to be perfectly reflecting).

Fig. 7. Instrumentation used for investigating joint noise radiation characteristics

The transmission loss was established by comparing the acceleration levels at the far end of the plain GRP beam to that across the joint at the end of the steel beam (the actual attenuation loss along the steel was measured to be much less than 0.25dB).

Waterborne Measurements

These measurements were intended to provide a qualitative assessment of the noise radiation characteristics of various joint configurations. In this case the same instrumentation was used as before, except the accelerometer was replaced by a small probe hydrophone. This was mounted on a traversing mechanism that allowed it to scan the length of the beam and joint 150mm from the face of the beam. The complete GRP beam, joint and steel substructure were then suspended vertically in an acoustic water tank facility until the top of the GRP beam with transducer were just proud of the water surface. The transducer was then excited with 10kHz tone bursts and the hydrophone used to monitor the signal radiated from various positions along the beam and joint. This test was carried out for waves travelling from both the GRP to Steel and Steel to GRP, the latter case being carried out by inverting the configuration and bonding the transducer to the end of the steel beam.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Reflection loss for the wedge joint is shown in figure 8. The results indicate a loss of more than 10dB above 6kHz rising to around 16.5dB at 12kHz. This is slightly higher than predicted and probably due to the forementioned inaccuracies of the predictive model and the fact that for practical reasons the wedge as constructed is not identical to that theoretically modelled. However, the general trend is comparable. Also shown for comparison purposes are the measured results for a straight forward GRP/steel butt joint and a joint where the GRP/steel interface has been tapered at an angle of 10degrees. As seen the GRP/steel butt joint is the worst case; the impedance mismatch between the GRP and steel is large hence the majority of the compressional wave energy is reflected back up the GRP. This joint provided a reflection loss of only 2dB at all frequencies tested. The tapered GRP/steel interface provided an improvement in reflection loss of typically 3 to 5.5dB over the frequency range 5 to 12kHz. The reason for this is that the tapering provided a gradual transition of the input impedance allowing more compressional wave energy to be transferred to the steel beam.

Measured transmission loss results are shown in figure 9. Once again the best performance was obtained from the viscoelastic joint which provided a transmission loss of more than 18dB from 6kHz upwards. This was again similar in trend at least to that predicted. The GRP/steel butt joint provided transmission loss of around 7dB due purely to impedance mismatch at the joint interface. The GRP/steel tapered joint interface has the worst transmission loss and indicated that although it provided a high reflection loss, it was at the expense of transmission loss, there was no actual absorption of compressional waves.

Fig. 8: Reflection loss

Fig. 9: Transmission loss

Waterborne Noise Radiation Characteristics

Fig. 10: Noise transmission GRP/steel

Fig. 11: Noise transmission Steel/GRP

The waterborne noise radiation characteristics are illustrated in figure 10 for the case where the compressional wave is propagating from GRP to steel. This would simulate the compressional waves generated by turbulent flow energy around a GRP sonar dome. The Y axis represents the radiated signal strength (as sensed by the hydrophone) at a point along side the GRP beam. The GRP/steel interface is ~1.40m from where the beam is being excited. The X axis represents the hydrophone position from the the excitation point alongside the beam. Also illustrated for comparison purposes are the noise radiation characteristics for a GRP/steel butt joint. As anticipated the butt joint is the worst case. The noise signal levels radiated from the GRP are typically ~-2dB except around the position 0.7m from the excitation point. Here there there is some constructive interference of the incoming tone burst and with that reflected at the GRP/Steel interface. Beyond the GRP/steel interface the radiated noise levels are reduced. This is because not all the compressional wave energy has been transmitted across the joint into the steel beam. With the viscoelastic wedge insert there is little constructive interference. As might be expected, close to the excitation point the radiated signal levels are about the same but further along the GRP beam at 1.0m from the excitation point, the radiated noise levels are some 8dB lower. However, at the joint itself there is an increase in the joint noise radiation characteristics again due to the impedance discontinuity at the joint interface. It is nevertheless some 3dB lower than the butt joint in this area. The noise

radiating from the joint can be isolated by application of an acoustic decoupling layer in the form of a thin layer of closed cell foam across the joint area. Further improvements to the reduction of radiated noise was achieved by application of a compressional wave damping material to the GRP.

The results for the compressional waves propagating from steel to GRP (this would be equivalent to ship structure-borne noise) are shown in figure 11. In all four cases the a high noise radiation hot spot is identified immediately behind the joint. The worst case is the butt joint where noise levels on the GRP side are high and dominated by that radiated by the joint itself. The inclusion of the viscoelastic wedge reduced the noise levels by up to 10dB on the GRP side compared to the butt joint. However, further improvements were obtained with the application the decoupling material and compressional wave damping material.

CONCLUSIONS

A simple study has been made into the use of a viscoelastic joint to reduce potential noise sources in GRP sonar domes. The study concerned the reduction of noise emitted by compressional waves, generated by (a) turbulent energy around the GRP dome and (b) structureborne vibrations from steel supporting structure. A simple predictive model and experimental measurements have confirmed the effectiveness of a viscoelastic interlayer in reducing compressional waves noise problems in the GRP when placed between the GRP and steel. The tests show that if the layer is tapered to the GRP in the form of a wedge 150mm long backed by a layer of the same material 100mm thick, the following results are obtained:

- (a) compressional waves propagating along the GRP are effectively terminated by the viscoelastic wedge, thereby reducing reflection of compressional waves back up the GRP; noise radiation from this source will therefore be reduced.
- (b) the viscoelastic wedge presents a considerable transmission loss to compressional waves travelling fro the steel supporting structure to the GRP once again providing a much quieter GRP structure than one incorporating a simple butt joint.
- (c) the noise reduction capabilities of a viscoelastic joint can be further enhanced by application of a decoupling layer to the joint and a compressional wave damping material to the GRP.

Together conclusions (a) and (b) indicate that as result of the use of the viscoelastic wedge insert compressional wave energy was effectively absorbed, i.e. little energy was reflected at the joint interface and little was transmitted across. The radiated noise characteristics were much lower than those of conventional butt joint technology. However, from the point of view of providing a quiet sonar dome, additional benefits were obtained by application of an acoustic decoupling coating to the joint area and compressional wave damping material to the GRP itself.

Although this work was carried out specifically to improve sonar performance and only compressional wave excitation has been considered, there are many implications for an energy absorbing joint of this nature. Its use in composite construction of mass transport vehicles could provide a much quieter environment for passengers. Furthermore, by considering shock and impact as dynamic events in the frequency domain and tuning the viscoelastic characteristic accordingly it may be possible to provide more damage tolerant composite structures.

GLOSSARY OF TERMS

Transmission Loss	$20\log$ (input acceleration/transmitted acceleration)
Reflection Loss	$20\log$ (input acceleration/reflected acceleration)

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